

Exploring the Gap Between Diagnosis and Treatment in Endometriosis: Evidence from German Statutory Health Insurance Claims Data

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Background: Endometriosis is a chronic disease characterised by the growth of endometrial-like tissue, glands, and stroma outside the uterine cavity, affecting the ovaries, pelvic and abdominal cavities, intestines, and peritoneum. It is the second most prevalent gynaecological disorder after fibroids, associated with dysmenorrhoea, dyspareunia, chronic pelvic pain, and infertility. Despite its substantial impact on life quality and productivity, the average diagnostic delay in Germany is seven years. Notably, the medical treatment of affected individuals remains insufficiently studied.

Objective: This study aimed to identify incident cases of endometriosis using German claims data and evaluate adherence of prescribed therapies to clinical guidelines.

Methods: This retrospective observational study utilised data from the *Deutsche Analysedatenbank* (DADB), containing German statutory health insurance (SHI) claims data from ~ 4.4 million insured individuals (2013-2023). The study included women aged 10-52 years with at least one or two fully observable baseline years, depending on the algorithm, and at least one outpatient or inpatient claim during both the preceding and reporting years.

Incident cases were identified using two approaches. The first applied the algorithm by Kohring (2024), developed from a nationwide analysis of contract doctors' billing data, primarily consisting of outpatient data. The second was based on endometriosis guidelines.

This study evaluated the proportion of incident endometriosis patients receiving first- and second-line medication according to clinical guidelines. First-line treatment included Dienogest and Norethisterone. Second-line treatment included other Progestogens (excluding first-line options), combined oral contraceptives, GnRH analogues, and Elagolix.

Results: Incidence rates differed substantially between the two algorithms. Kohring's (2024) approach showed an increase from 5.21 per 1,000 in 2015 to 7.88 per 1,000 in 2023, whereas the guideline-based approach showed an increase from 1.25 per 1,000 in 2015 to 1.67 per 1,000 by 2023. In 2023, 86% and 76% of the identified patients had no prior therapy. Among those diagnosed in 2022 who were fully observable in the follow-up year, 13% and 17% received first-line medication, and 8% and 13% received second-line treatment.

Implications for research: The increasing number of endometriosis diagnoses contrasts with the consistently low rate of diagnostic laparoscopies. Increased media coverage may have led to earlier diagnoses in individuals with milder symptoms who were less likely to undergo laparoscopy. Claims data suggest that only a small proportion of incident patients received guideline-adherent medication. This may have resulted from patients covering medication costs themselves or inadequate guideline implementation. Further research is needed to explore barriers to guideline adherence and improve treatment accessibility.